

COMPREHENSIVE GENETIC VARIANCE MODELS FOR HEALTH AND DISEASE -ROLE OF EPIGENETICS

Dr.V.Venugopal Rao ,

Department of Genetics and Bio Medical Sciences

St. Ann's college for women Mehdiapatnam Hyderabad 500 028 Telangana,India.

Abstract : A value addition has been given to the concept of genetic variance existing which is refined by inclusion of epigenetic variance and ANOVA model is discussed to delineate the levels of expression. It may be useful for health and disease management, a future vision.

Key words: genetic variance, quantitative variation, epigenetics, epigenomics, gene expression

Introduction & Discussion

A comprehensive genetic model ($V_P=V_G+V_{EPI}+V_E$) has been proposed where V_P is total variance in phenotype; V_G is variance due to genes ; V_{EPI} is variance due to epigenetic modification ; V_E is variance by environment alone to reorient the basic notation

$$V_P=V_G+V_E(1)$$

Another model is possible for genetic variance alone when epigenetic modifications are through germinal cells i.e. gametes and are heritable for few generations which is referred as genomic imprinting for example chromosome 15. If it happens through eggs from mother it leads to Angelman Syndrome; through sperm it causes Prader Villie syndrome (2).Such phenomena includes by default the variance due to epigenetics V_{EPI} ; where the proposed model is $V_G=V_A+V_D+V_I+V_{EPI}$ an extension of $V_G=V_A+V_D+V_I$ where V_G is variance due to genes, V_A is variance due to additive gene action, V_D is variance due to dominant action of genes, V_I is variance due to gene interaction (epistasis), V_{EPI} is due to variance to due to epigenetic changes.

This model can be understood and applied for both qualitative and quantitative traits equivocally; since all major genes with distinct phenotypic effect are also always under epigenetic modifications(without mutational changes in sequences) exhibiting environmental variability .Many a times gene expression variation study is feasible with levels of RNA or protein expressed. There is no stringent border line delineating quantitative and qualitative traits in terms of their magnitude of gene expression .

In nature all the traits are quantitative irrespective of whether they are monogenic or polygenic because of two very important phenomena; one is penetrance and expressivity

Penetrance is referred to percentage of expression in the possessors of a given gene ;whereas expressivity refers to magnitude of expression in terms of RNA or protein levels in the possessors of a gene ;However there is always a small component of non expression of a

gene by possessors. That means having a gene itself is not sufficient to express unless it is triggered by environmental factors such as life style, food habits ,habitats, stress factors and addiction (3). Some of the evidences are available from disorders viz Huntington’s chorea ,G6PD deficiency being single gene disorders , Alzheimer’s and Parkinsons with complex mode of inheritance

Many so called life style disorders which are multifactorial are reported to have triggering factors viz age , occupation, emotional stress ,addiction(smoking,alcohol) for hypertension, Diabetes ,thyroids, obesity.

V_{EPI} and V_E are measurable within a particular variety , genotype or a specific disease with a single gene origin whose expression can vary with respect to a niche or habit. Here we can propose two way ANOVA where one factor is genotype ;second factor being a specific environment; natural or created in the experimental setup to study magnitude of expression of a genotype in terms of RNA or protein expressed under different niches. Total variance (V_P) can be measured which can be partitioned into between genotype variance , between environmental variance (V_{EPI}) and residual variance or remaining variance V_E ; being unattributable to any cause implies that a part of V_E is always attributable to known causes of epigenetics or epigenomics.

Epigenetic variance is also measurable in terms of extent of DNA methylation, Histone methylation and acetylation with in a specific niche or environment for a given genotype.

Hypothetical model choices proposed

Table 1: Distribution of RNA expression levels an health indicator for obesity markers in different groups of ethnicity

Groups each with 5 values

Group 1	Group2	Group 3	Group 4	
X_{11}	X_{12}	X_{13}	X_{14}	RT_1
X_{21}	X_{22}	X_{23}	X_{24}	RT_2
X_{31}	X_{32}	X_{34}	X_{35}	RT_3
X_{41}	X_{42}	X_{43}	X_{44}	RT_4
X_{51}	X_{52}	X_{53}	X_{55}	RT_5
CT_1	CT_2	CT_3	CT_4	GT

Where X_{ij} is individual RNA expression levelvalue for a given cell ,an intersection between row and column

Algorithm for analysis

CF = Correction Factor = GT^2/N where GT is Grand Total = $CT_1+CT_2+CT_3+CT_4$ OR $RT_1+RT_2+RT_3+RT_4+RT_5$

TSS= $\sum X_{ij}^2$ -CF where TSS is total sum of squares

$BSS = \sum CT_j^2 - CF$; where $\sum CT_j^2 = CT_1^2/n_1 + CT_2^2/n_2 + CT_3^2/n_3 + CT_4^2/n_4$ where n_i is number of individuals per column i.e. ethnic group where BSS is between sum of squares

TSS-BSS = ESS Error Sum of squares which could be environmental, GXE interaction at phenotype level and epigenetics at molecular expression levels much focused.

Source of variation	df =degrees of freedom	Mean =sum of squares /df
TSS	N- number of columns -number of rows 20-4-5 =11	TSS/11
BSS	Number of columns-1 (4-1) =3	BSS/3
ESS Residual	df of tss-df of bss = 8	ESS/8

F ratio = Mean BSS/Mean ESS where 3 is numerator degrees of freedom and 8 is denominator degrees of freedom

F table defined by both degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance (α los) type 1 error probability i.e probability of rejecting null hypothesis when it is true in real sense (4).

Other choices of application

- 1. Variation in the levels expression of a biomarker(DNA, RNA ,Proteins) in severity levels where degree of expression influences a disease in man**
- 2. Expression levels of biomarkers in varieties of plants for their role in yield, disease causation, disease resistance, saline tolerance , stress physiology and antioxidant expression**
- 3. Utility in animal breeding to study expression levels in heath and disease**

Now state of the art technology viz microarrays ,PCR ,next gen sequencing allow us to decipher dissect out, delineate, include and exclude different possibilities of sequences and their expression levels.

Proposed Epigenetic mechanisms by other authors as background of the present model :

“Epigenetics,” refers to the complex interactions between the genes and the environment leading to overall development in living organisms. this term is also relevant to heritable changes that are not due to changes in DNA sequence but due to epigenetic modifications, such as DNA methylation and histone modification, altered DNA accessibility and chromatin structure, thereby regulating patterns of gene expression.

Th cell lineages in the embryo and adult organism are destined for a function through these mechanisms. They can be modified by external influences, or internal influences causing alterations of phenotype or Patho phenotype. Besides, epigenetic programming has a crucial role in the regulation of pluripotency genes, which become inactivated after differentiation. The identified chemical changes are methylation and acetylation for example by homocysteine, presence of which leads to complex cardiovascular diseases, also a clue to therapeutic solutions for such agents through vitamin B supplements leading to future directions(6).

Epigenetic modifications are involved in regulation of transcriptional activity while somatically heritable and reversible, making them good therapeutic candidates but mutations are irreversible where treatment is remote possibility ; these mechanisms have been going on to be administered in the medical world to reverse cancer state of cells to normalcy by drugs which can induce reversion of epigenetic modifications.

Epigenetic changes can anticipate disease pathology and thus serve as diagnostic indicators for risk, and can act as prognostic indicators for disease progression. Histone deacetylase inhibitors and DNA methylation inhibitors are FDA approved drugs and are clinically successful. In addition, histone methylation and microRNAs have also received attention as potential therapeutic targets (7)

Epigenetics are the heritable changes in gene expression patterns which occur without altering DNA sequence and they reversible some times . Epigenetic modifications are induced by DNA methylation, histone modification, and RNA-mediated mechanisms which alter the gene expression, primarily at the transcriptional level. Such specific type of alterations some times help regulate genome activity through transcriptional silencing of transposable elements thereby contributing toward genomic stability. Epigenetic modifications are important during the development of male and female gametes, fertilization, embryogenesis, fruit formation, and seed germination in plants (8).

Cervical cancer (CC) is an important public health concern for women, where Human papilloma virus_(HPV) has been recognized as a major contributor to CC development, besides epigenetic changes which also may cause other autoimmune diseases,. The major factors identified are DNA methylation, histone modification, untranslated RNA regulation and chromatin regulation. Such studies are helpful for early screening, risk assessment, molecular targeted therapy and prognostic prediction of CC (9).

Epigenetics plays an important role in a variety of metabolic diseases, such as diabetes, obesity, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), osteoporosis, gout, hyperthyroidism, hypothyroidism and others(10).

Experimental techniques for evaluating epigenomes at the single-cell level provide a better understanding of epigenetic processes and their complex interactions with gene regulation. Recent technological advances have made it possible to also evaluate and identify the dynamics of epigenetic maintenance and reprogramming at the single-cell level

Epigenomics another word introduced to define and explain as the quantification and integrated study of the modifications made to DNA and histones, Mutations in DNA are the main cause for individual differences which are inherited, besides epigenomic changes are also inherited but some times reversible whereas mutations in DNA are rarely reversible Excess methylation and hydroxy methylation of DNA lower the expression levels in general. The addition of acetyl, methyl, phosphorus, or ubiquitin tails to histones to alter transcription and the binding of small untranslated RNAs, known as microRNAs (miRNA), that bind

m RNA and block its translation are other sources of epigenomics

Epigenomic research revealed maternal smoking and air pollution lead to heritable DNA methylation patterns in Asthma patients. Epigenetic changes have also been identified in a variety of other allergic diseases, such as respiratory in nature, some of these are treated with oral immune therapy to develop tolerance to these allergies (11).

Epigenetic modifications are most of the times reversible, offering promising new therapeutic approaches for treating these diseases using epigenetic modulators (12).

Conclusion; Genetic variations in different populations can be better understood; role of epigenetics or epigenomics in causing such variation can be meaningfully deciphered which may provide solutions for health, disease management and anticipatory counselling in children who may become victims to a disease in such populations; which is future direction of epigenomic research.

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